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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3

REPORT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF STANDARD OPERATING PROCEDURES (SOPS) FOR THE *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS* MLST SCHEMES

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project: JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – PARASite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>)

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE–WP3 Design, implementation and validation of MLST schemes

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP3-T3 Development of SOPs for the *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* MLST schemes

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1. Background

The PARADISE project aims to deliver informative typing schemes and innovative detection strategies applicable to food matrices for the food-borne parasites *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia*. Using genomics and metagenomics, the project is generating much needed data to enrich our understanding of the epidemiology and genomics of these organisms, and provide the basis for development and testing of improved strain-typing schemes. In parallel, strategies (nanobodies, aptamers, use of hybridization probes) to enrich for the target pathogens in different matrices are under development and validation. These new methodologies will form the basis for integrated approaches to control *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* in the European food chain.

The objectives of PARADISE WP3 are:

- To select new markers *in silico* for robust high resolution genotyping of *C. parvum* and *Giardia duodenalis* using whole genome data generated in WP2-T1, unpublished data from within the consortium and publically available data
- To develop multilocus sequence typing (MLST) schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis*
- To conduct an inter-laboratory comparison of MLST schemes

The procedures undertaken to develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that can be followed to perform the experiments needed for the MLST schemes for *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* are described in the deliverable:

Deliverable D-JRP-PARADISE-WP3.3: Report on the development of SOPs for the *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* MLST schemes

2. *Cryptosporidium parvum*

Standard operating procedure for subtyping *Cryptosporidium parvum* by nested PCR amplification and sequencing of eight selected markers

Date: 09.09.2022

Key Words: PCR, *Cryptosporidium parvum*, MLST subtyping

Authors: Simone M. Cacciò (ISS), Martha Betson (UoS), Karin Troell (SVA)

Description of procedure

Cryptosporidium parvum is the most important zoonotic species in the genus *Cryptosporidium*. It causes gastrointestinal disease in humans and other animals, particularly young ruminants, and has a global distribution. Infection is transmitted by direct faecal-oral contact or by ingestion of water and food contaminated with parasite oocysts. Due to the lack of morphological differences among oocysts, molecular biology techniques are used to distinguish isolates and to support epidemiological investigations. To date, a standardized genotyping scheme is not available and most studies have relied upon sequence analysis of the highly polymorphic glycoprotein 60 (*gp60*) gene. Analysis of a single gene cannot be used as a reliable proxy for the genetic identity of an isolate. To address this problem, we have performed a large whole genome comparative study and identified eight novel polymorphic gene markers, each located on one of the eight *C. parvum* chromosomes (Annex 1). We designed

primers for nested PCR reactions to amplify these markers (Annex 2), which should be analysed by Sanger sequencing.

Equipment, materials and reagents

General note: The described method is based on standard PCR procedures and all reagents may therefore be replaced by equivalent reagents or methods established in your laboratory. Here we provide information on the reagents and materials that have been used in expert laboratories (ISS, SVA, UoS) to establish the procedure. Notably, the procedure for Sanger sequencing may be different (in-house sequencing vs. commercial provider) between laboratories.

1. DNA samples (usually DNA extractions from faecal samples) which have tested positive for *Cryptosporidium parvum*
2. Primers (prepare 10µM working solutions in H₂O from 100mM stocks), see list of primer sequences in Annex 1
3. PCR Kit: The method has been established at ISS using the Hot StarTaq Master Mix (Qiagen, catalog number 203446), which comes as a ready to use solution (2X) containing buffer, MgCl₂ (3mM) and dNTPs.

Note: alternative PCR polymerase and buffer systems may be used; however, optimization of PCR conditions might be necessary

4. Ultrapure PCR grade H₂O for molecular biology (e.g. HPLC grade)
5. PCR tubes, strips or plates suitable for 50µl PCR reactions
6. Standard PCR thermocycler
7. Standard equipment for agarose gel-electrophoresis
8. Agarose electrophoresis running buffer (e.g. 1x Tris-acetate-EDTA (TAE) buffer)
9. Ethidium bromide solution or equivalent ethidium bromide alternative
10. Standard loading buffer for agarose gel electrophoresis (e.g., DNA Gel Loading Dye (6X), ThermoFisher, catalog number: R0611)
11. Adequate DNA marker for agarose gel electrophoresis (e.g. 1 kb Ladder NEB catalog number: N3232)
12. Optional: ExoSAP-IT for PCR product cleanup (Thermo Fisher #78201.1.ML) or equivalent PCR clean-up procedure used to prepare DNA for subsequent Sanger sequencing
13. Optional: BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (Applied Biosystems 4337457), if Sanger sequencing reaction will be set-up in-house

Time considerations

Preparation of master mixes 1+2 and PCR 1: approximately 30 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

PCR 1 running time (depending on the thermocycler): approximately 2.5 h

Preparation of PCR 2: approximately 15 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

PCR 2 running time (depending on the thermocycler): approximately 2.5 h

Clean-up of PCR-products for Sanger sequencing: approximately 45 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

Preparation of sequencing reaction: approximately 15 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

Sequencing Reaction 2.5 h (if run in-house)

Procedure (step-by-step instructions)

1. Prepare master mix for both PCR reactions at once and store on ice.

Notes: Prepare master mix for 50µl (1st PCR) and 50µl (2nd PCR) final volume
 Always prepare a 10% excess volume of the master mix and include one negative control (water instead of DNA) per primer pair and a positive control. The positive control is omitted in cases where pre-tested material is used (e.g. in specific ring trial applications)

50 µl reaction	Final conc.	1st PCR 1 x (µl)	x__samples	2nd PCR 1 x (µl)	x__samples
Hot StarTaq Master Mix (Qiagen) 2X	1 x	25		25	
FW primer 10 µM	400 nM	2		2	
RV primer 10 µM	400 nM	2		2	
H ₂ O (HPLC grade)		16*		16*	
total		45*		45*	

*depending on the amount of template, adjust the volume of water to obtain a final volume of 50 µl

2. Prepare PCR reaction for 1st PCR using 2-5 µl of extracted DNA as template and 2 µl of H₂O for the negative control (for expected product sizes see Annex 2)
3. Running conditions for 1st PCR:
 - 1) initial denaturation: 95°C - 15 min
 - 2) 35 cycles: 95°C - 30 sec, 58°C - 30 sec, 72°C - 60 sec
 - 3) final extension: 72°C - 7 min
 - 4) hold: 4°C - hold
4. Prepare PCR reaction for 2nd PCR using 5 µl of the 1st PCR reaction as template and 5 µl of H₂O for the negative control (expected product sizes see Annex 2)
 Note: open vials with PCR products (e.g. after 1st PCR) very carefully. **Take extreme caution to avoid carry-over contamination. Ideally, prepare the second PCR reactions in a separate room or cabinet and use a different pipette set. If not possible, at least add the template from the first PCR reactions to the second PCR mix in a separate room.**
5. Running conditions for 2nd PCR:
 - 1) initial denaturation: 95°C - 15 min
 - 2) 35 cycles: 95°C - 30 sec, 58°C - 30 sec, 72°C - 60 sec
 - 3) final extension: 72°C - 7 min
 - 4) hold: 4°C hold
6. Check nested PCR reaction (2nd PCR) on a 1.2% agarose gel and document the gel picture. To do this mix 5-10 µl of PCR reaction with appropriate amount of loading buffer and load gel. Use appropriate DNA marker to estimate the size and the amount of the PCR products.
7. Analyse PCR products by Sanger sequencing. Use the procedure and materials established in your laboratory, either to perform in-house reactions or to send purified (or even unpurified) PCR products to a commercial provider.

Annex 1. Sequences of the eight markers included in the *C. parvum* genotyping scheme. The positions of the nested PCR primers are highlighted in green.

Marker CP003930

GAAAATGAATGCAATACACAACAA TTGCTTATATCGTTGGGTAAGCAAAAAAAGAAAATGGAAAA
GATGAATTCAAGTTTGTAGAGGGTTTGTTTTAAACGATTCCGTTGAATCAAGATCTAGTCGTGGA
TTTAAGGTGAATTTCAAATACAAGAATTCATCCATTAATATAGCTTCCAAATCAAATCCAACCCAA
ACTTTATTATTCATACTTGTATTGCAAACATTAATAAACAACACGAAATGGAATTTGTCAGTGCAG
ATTCATTAATTTCCCTGATAATAATTCCAACCTAATACCGCTTTAATCGTGCATTTCATCAAGTTCT
GATTATTTATGTAATCAACTTTACTTAAGAAAAATGAATTCCTTCTTATTCCGAAATATACCTTAA
TATAGAACGGAACCTAATAACAAGC **AAAGTATCATCTTCTTAATAGCG**

Marker CP0028230

CTGCTAAGCCTCAATATTGTTCAA CAATGAACTTCCACTGAATGGAGTCGGTAAAAAATCCTG
TTTTACAAAGTGGAGTAAAGGAACATAATTTAGAACTTCCCTATGAAGATAAATTTAAAGCCATCTT
TCCATTTTATCTAGAAGCCC GAAGACTATACCTAGCGAACTAAACAAAATAAATCTTAGATGGAAA
GTAGAAAATACAGGCGCAGAGAGATCAAGTTCGGATAACAGAAAAACGGTCCCAGATCTGGAAT
GCTTGGAGGGCCTATTCAACATAGTGCTGAAGGAATGGATACTTACCATGCAACTTATGTTGAGG
TTGATGATTCTCTGATGAGGAGGACACAATTAATCCAGTTGGTCTCCGGACGCAGACCCAAGC
GTCGCACAAATTTTGAAGCTATTAGAGCTTGATATAGATCTGAAAACAATGAAGAAGCTG **TGGAT**
CATAATCAAAATGGCA

Marker CP0031960

TAGAGTTAGGGCTTAAATGAGGAA AATCTTTAATATTAATAACGTTATGGTTTTCTAGATCGTCTTG
GTGCCTGAAATTCGAGATTTGAGTAGAATTATAATATTAGAAATAGAACTGGTAAATAGGTAAAG
CTTACCTGGATGAAATTCATGTAGAAGTTGAGTATAGCATAGATCTTGAAAGACTAGTAGGCTGA
GTTTGGGGACAATAAGTGAGAATAGAGGGAATTTGTTTTCTTGAGTATCAAGAGAGGGATTCCAA
AAATCGAATAAAGTGTCAGATTCTAATGAGATGATTGCGACTCTTGGGTAATAAAGAGGGCCATC
CTTGTGAGGAAGAATCCCTTTGTATTGTTTCATATTGATTGATTAGTACATGGTTTGGAGTTTCTTCT
TTTGAAAATATATTGTAATCTACTAAAGATTGAGAAATAGATTCTAACCATTCAGGTAATCTTTCT
GATTAACAATTCCTGATTCAGAGACTGTTCTCCCATACTTGAGTTTGTCTTCCGTTCAATTTTAC
ATTTAGAAATGAGGATCTTGAGATATTCTCTAG **TAATGCTTTTCTGTTCTGAGT**

Marker CP0021750

ACTGAAACTTCAACACCCAGGAA TTGCTTTGGACATATATCAAGATCAAAAACAAGATCAAATC
AAAATCAAGATCAAATCAAGATCAAATCAAGATCAAATCAAAATCAAGAGCAAGATCAAATC
AAGAACAAGAGCAAGATCAAATCAAGATCAAGATCAAGAACAAGATCAAGAACAAGATCAAGAT
CAAGATCAAGAACAAGATCAAGAACAAGGTCAAGAACAAGATCAAGAACAAGATCAAGATCAAAC
TTAGATTCTGAACTCGATTCAGGAACTAGTAAAACAGAGTGACAGAAGGTAGTTCTGTACTTGCT
GAACCTTTTAAATCAAATTTTTGAAGATGTTTGTGAAAGAGCCCTTAGAAGATTCTACTCCTTCAG
TAATGAAATTTTTAGTATTTTCATATCAAATGAGCCAACCTGTTACAGTAATGTCAGAGGCTAAAGA
AATTTTTAATGAAGTCAAAA **TGCTTTTTGGAAACGGCCAGATT**

Marker CP0024650

AGAGCAACTTCCATCTCACTTTTA GGTGGAAGCTTGAAATAAGGGATTTAATATTAGAAAAGA
ACTTTTTGATGATTTATCTTTCCCAATCAGTTTAAGTGATGGAATTGTTGGAAAAGTTAATATTGAT
GTTATCTGGAGAAAAATTTACCCAAGAGTTTGTGAAAATCACCTTGGATGATGTATATGTTATTT
TTAATACTACTGATATGAAAAATTGGAATGTTGAAATGTTTAAAAAACTGGAAAAGGGTTAAAG
CTAATCTATTAACAAGATGAATTTACTTTCTTAAAAAGTGCTATGGCTTCCAATTTTCTCAA
CAAATTGGACACTTTTTTATATCAAAGATTGATTTGAAATTAACAACATCAATTTTGAATTGAAAA
TTTGTATTCCACTATATGAAGAGATTTGTTATTGGACTAAGTATTGATAAATTTCCAGTCGAAAT
TGTAATGAATATTGGATTCCAGTAGATAAATC **GGAGGAGCCATTTAGCCGTAAT**

Marker CP0012400

CCTACACGTCCTTATGGCCCTGGT GAAAAGTTACCTCCACATCTATCTCCATTTGTGGATGATAGT
 ACCCAAGGTTATATTCCAACCTCAGAGACAAGTTCTTGATGAAATTAAGGAATCCAATAGTCATAAA
 TCTCAATCTTGCTTATCTGAAGATGAATCAACAGAAATTGATGAACTTTCAGAACATGATTCTGATA
 TTGAAGTTCAACAAGCTAGAGAAGATGCCTACTTTGATTCTATTGAGAGAGAACAATCATTATCAA
 CCTCAAATGAAATTGATTCAATTGATAACGAGCATAAAGATTTCATCCAATTTTACAACAGAATCTGA
 ATTAACTAATACAAAAGATAAAGTAAATATTGCTAGAAAAGCTCGCGAAGAAACGTAAAGAAGAGGA
 ACAAAGAGAACAACAAAAGACTCTACTCAAAAAGAAGCATAAGAGACTTTTACAAAGAATTGAATA
 TTCTAACAAAATCGC**TTCCGAGAAAGCAGAAAGGTGGA**

Marker CP007000

GACTACAACCTGGAAGCTCTTAGTA GTATACTGGTACTCATAAAGTTAATAGAAGCTGGAATTGAAA
 GGATTATTCTGTTTCCTGGATGGTTTACTATGGAGTTAAGAGATTTAAGGTAATAGACCAATAAGT
 TAACATGAGGAACAAAAGATTCTTGTAGGCCTGTAAATCCAAGATTCTTGAATGATGAAGTAATTA
 AACCAGTATTTTGGGATACATGTCCAAACTCTGGGACTGTTGAGAAATAGCTTGGCCTTTGTTTAA
 ACTTAAAGTTTGGAGAAGCAATCTGCGATTAATTGTGGCTTTGAGATGAATTCTCTGGCAAAGTTAA
 TTAAGATATGATTCAAAGGAGACTAAACATGTCTGTTTCTGTAATTTTCAATCCAGATCTTTGGAG
 GGACAAAATAATCTCAGCTGAGTAATACTCATAGAATAGGAATTCAGGATTAGTATCGTAAACACA
 TAACTTGAGAAGCTGAGATCTTTCGTAGGAAATCAGAAGAAATCTTGTGAGATCTTTAGCTGACTT
 TAAAA**TTGTATTGGCTCAAAGAGTTTC**

Marker CP001010

TAAGTAGAGCAATCCCAGTAACA CACCACATGAACAGGTAATTACTACTGTCGATAACACACAAA
 CATATTCTGTTAGAGAGGTTAGAACAGAAGACAATGAAATTCGCCGTTCTTCTCAGTATAATAGTG
 CTAATGTGAAGCCAATAAACTTGCATGAAAACCAATAGGAACAGAAATTAACAATACAAATGGAA
 ATTTTGAACCTAGAAGAAAGTCTAGCAACCTTATATTAATTAGAGACATTGAGACTCAGAGCCTTA
 AAGATAAGAATGATAACCACAGTCTTACTATAGAAAAACAAGGAACAGAGGAAGAAAAAAGAAACT
 CAAATGACTATCATCACCTCCGCCTCCATCATCATATTCCAACCAAAAACCAAGCAAATTTAGTTC
 CTCATATTGGTAAAGTATGCGAAGAAAAAGAATCTGAAATTTCTAACAGGGGAATTTATACAAAGAA
 ATAACAACCATGAATATATTGAAACACAATCTTACCTCATCAAAACACTAAGAAAATACAAAAAA
GAAGCCTCCAATATCTCTTAGCTC

Annex 2. List of the primer sequences used to amplify the eight *C. parvum* gene markers. Primers for nested PCR (2nd PCR) are highlighted in grey.

Marker	Oligoname	Sequence (5' – 3')	Amplicon size (bp)
Cp0039030	39030For	ACTGTCAGCATGGAAAATGAATGC	469
Cp0039030	39030Rev	CTGGCTCGCTATTAAGGAAGATGA	
Cp0039030	39030NesFor	GAAAATGAATGCAATACACAACAA	450
Cp0039030	39030NesRev	CGCTATTAAGGAAGATGATACTTT	
Cp0028230	28230For	TTATCGTACCTGCTAAGCCTCAAT	498
Cp0028230	28230Rev	GTCTATTACCGGTGCCATTTTGAT	
Cp0028230	28230NesFor	CTGCTAAGCCTCAATATTGTTCAA	478
Cp0028230	28230NesRev	TGCCATTTTGATTATGATCCA	
Cp0031960	31960For	GGTAGAGTTAGGGCTTAAATGAGG	595
Cp0031960	31960Rev	TGGATTACTCCAGAACAGGAAAAG	
Cp0031960	31960NesFor	TAGAGTTAGGGCTTAAATGAGGAA	587

Cp0031960	31960NesRev	ACTCCAGAACAGGAAAAGACATTA	
Cp0021750	21750For	ATTGGAACTGAAACTTCAACACCC	509
Cp0021750	21750Rev	TGTAATCTGGCCGTTTCCAAAAAG	
Cp0021750	21750NesFor	ACTGAAACTTCAACACCCCAGGAA	507
Cp0021750	21750NesRev	AATCTGGCCGTTTCCAAAAAGCAA	
Cp0024650	24650For	AACAAGAGCAACTTTCCATCTCAC	536
Cp0024650	24650Rev	GTCTGTATTACGGCCTAAAATGGC	
Cp0024650	24650NesFor	AGAGCAACTTTCCATCTCACTTTTA	526
Cp0024650	24650NesRev	ATTACGGCCTAAAATGGCTCCTCCA	
Cp0012400	12400For	AGATTACCTACACGTCCTTATGGC	512
Cp0012400	12400Rev	GATTCCAACCTTTCTGCTTTCTCC	
Cp0012400	12400NesFor	CCTACACGTCCTTATGGCCCTGGT	503
Cp0012400	12400NesRev	TCCAACCTTTCTGCTTTCTCCGAA	
Cp0007000	07000For	TACTTGACTACAACCTGGAAGCTCT	568
Cp0007000	07000Rev	AGCTAGGAAACTCTTTGAGCCAAT	
Cp0007000	07000NesFor	GACTACAACCTGGAAGCTCTTAGTA	558
Cp0007000	07000NesRev	GGAAACTCTTTGAGCCAATACAAA	
Cp0001010	01010For	GCCATAACTAGAGCAATCCCAGTA	560
Cp0001010	01010Rev	CCAGACCTAAGAGATATTGGAGGC	
Cp0001010	01010NesFor	TAAGTAGAGCAATCCCAGTAACAA	553
Cp0001010	01010NesRev	GACCTAAGAGATATTGGAGGCTTC	

3. *Giardia duodenalis*

Standard operating procedure for subtyping *Giardia duodenalis* Assemblage B by nested PCR amplification and sequencing of seven selected markers

Date: 09.09.2022

Key Words: PCR, *Giardia*, MLST subtyping assemblage B

Authors: Elke Radam, Christian Klotz, Robert Koch-Institute Berlin

Description of procedure

Giardia duodenalis represents a species complex discriminating eight genetically distinguishable assemblages (A – H). Human disease is mainly caused by potentially zoonotic assemblages A and B, which are not distinguishable by routine diagnostics. Adequate in vitro culture systems are also not applicable in routine diagnostic laboratory procedures. Therefore, genotyping is mainly performed from bulk DNA preparation of enriched cysts or of total stool samples. *Giardia* parasites possess tetraploid genomes (16n in the cysts) with different grades of allelic sequence heterozygosity (ASH). In assemblage B (~ 0.5%), ASH per bp is typically greater than in assemblage A (typically < 0,05%). Therefore, different strategies for molecular typing of assemblage A and B are required to achieve the same power of resolution. For assemblage A, a typing procedure was recently implemented based on 6 newly defined markers (Ankarklev et al. 2028). Here, a new MLST scheme for assemblage B using 7 newly defined genome markers is described.

- Ankarklev, J., M. Lebbad, E. Einarsson, O. Franzen, H. Ahola, K. Troell, and S.G. Svard, A novel high-resolution multilocus sequence typing of *Giardia intestinalis* Assemblage A isolates reveals zoonotic transmission, clonal outbreaks and recombination. *Infect Genet Evol*, 2018, 60, 7-16.

Equipment, materials and reagents

General note: The described method is based on standard PCR procedures and all reagents may therefore be replaced by equivalent material or methods established in your lab. Here we provide exemplarily the reagents and materials that have been used in our lab to establish the procedure. Particularly the Sanger sequencing procedure may be different (in-house vs. external) between labs.

14. DNA samples (usually DNA extractions from fecal samples) tested positive for *Giardia* assemblage B
15. Primers (prepare 10µM working solutions in H₂O from 100mM stocks), see list of primer sequences in Annex 1
16. PCR Kit: The method has been established using the Dream Taq polymerase including a 10x buffer (Thermo Fisher # EP0701), which already includes MgCl₂. A final MgCl₂ concentration of 3mM in the PCR reaction must be achieved (e.g. by using a separate 25 mM MgCl₂stock solution (see below))
Note: alternative PCR polymerase and buffer systems may be used, however, optimization of PCR conditions might be necessary
17. MgCl₂ (25mM stock, e.g. Thermo Fisher # R0971)
18. dNTP stock (40mM = 10mM for each nucleotide) (e.g. Carl Roth K039.2)
19. Ultrapure PCR grade H₂O for molecular biology (e.g. HPLC grade)
20. PCR tubes, stripes or plates suitable for 50µl PCR reactions
21. Standard PCR-cycler
22. Agarose gel-electrophoresis standard equipment
23. Agarose electrophoresis running buffer (e.g. 1x Tris-acetate-EDTA (TAE) buffer)
24. Midori Green Advanced (Biozym 617004) or equivalent ethidium bromide alternative

25. Standard sample buffer for agarose gel electrophoresis, we use a homemade 6x standard sample buffer containing 0,25% bromophenol blue
26. Adequate DNA marker for agarose gel (e.g. 1 kb Ladder NEB N3232)
27. Optional: ExoSAP-IT for PCR product cleanup (Thermo Fisher #78201.1.ML) or equivalent PCR clean-up procedure used to prepare DNA for subsequent Sanger sequencing.
28. Optional: BigDye Terminator v3.1 Cycle Sequencing Kit (Applied Biosystems 4337457), if Sanger sequencing reaction will be set-up in-house

Time considerations

Preparation of master mixes 1+2 and PCR 1: approximately 30 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

PCR 1 running time (depending on cyclor): approximately 2,5 h

Preparation of PCR 2: approximately 15 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

PCR 2 running time (depending on cyclor): approximately 2,5 h

Clean-up of PCR-products for Sanger sequencing: approximately 45 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

Preparation of sequencing reaction: approximately 15 minutes (dependent on number of samples)

Sequencing Reaction 2,5 h

Procedure (step-by-step instructions)

8. Prepare master mix for both PCR reactions at once and store on ice.

Notes: Prepare master mix for 50µl (1st PCR) and 50µl (2nd PCR) final volume
Always prepare master mix for 10% excess volume and include one negative control (water instead of DNA) per primer pair and a positive control. Positive control is omitted in case pre-tested material is used (e.g. in specific ring trial applications)

50 µl reaction	Final conc.	1st PCR 1 x (µl)	x__samples	2nd PCR 1 x (µl)	x__samples
Taq PCR buffer 10 x (Thermo Fisher # EP0701)*	1 x (incl. 2 mM MgCl ₂)	5		5	
MgCl ₂ 25 mM*	1 mM	2		2	
dNTP 10 µM each	200 nM	1		1	
Dream Taq polymerase 5U/µl	1.25 U	0,5		0,5	
FW primer 10 µM	400 nM	2		2	
RV primer 10 µM	400 nM	2		2	
H ₂ O (HPLC grade)		35,5		36	
total		48		48,5	

* final MgCl₂ concentration is 3mM

9. Prepare PCR reaction for 1st PCR by using 2 µl of extracted DNA as template and 2 µl of H₂O for the negative control (for expected product sizes see Annex 1)

10. Running conditions for 1st PCR:

1) initial denaturation: 95°C - 3 min
2) 35 cycles: 95°C - 30 sec, 58°C - 30 sec, 72°C - 60 sec
3) final extension: 72°C - 7 min
4) hold: 4°C for ever

11. Prepare PCR reaction for 2nd PCR by using 1.5 µl of PCR reaction 1 as template and 1.5 µl of H₂O for the negative control (expected product sizes see Annex 1)

Note: open vials with PCR products (e.g. after 1st PCR) very carefully. **Take extreme caution to avoid carry-over contamination. Ideally, prepare second PCR in separate rooms or cabinets and use a different pipette set.**

12. Running conditions for 2nd PCR:

1) initial denaturation: 95°C - 3 min
2) 35 cycles: 95°C - 30 sec, 58°C - 30 sec, 72°C - 60 sec
3) final extension: 72°C - 7 min
4) hold: 4°C for ever

13. Check nested PCR reaction (2nd PCR) on a 1.2% agarose gel and document the gel picture. Mix 5-10 µl of PCR reaction with appropriate amount of sample buffer and load gel. Use appropriate DNA marker to be able to estimate the size and the amount of PCR product.

14. Analyse PCR products by Sanger sequencing. Use the procedure and materials established in your lab. In the following steps our in-house procedure is described to prepare the PCR clean-up and in-house sequencing reaction.

Following steps are optional depending on the standard procedure used in your laboratory to Sanger sequence PCR products.

15. Calculate the DNA-amount to be used for PCR clean-up (optimal 10-20 ng in final sequencing reaction). Use DNA quantification method established in your lab, eg. OD260/280 nm, Quantus measurements, etc.
16. Clean up PCR product with ExoSAP-IT (follow manufacture's protocol).
- Mix 5 µl PCR product (usually approximately 1:10 diluted, dependent on DNA quantification results) with 2 µl ExoSAP reagent.
 - Incubate at 37°C for 15 min to degrade excess primers and nucleotides
 - Incubate at 85°C for 15 min to inactivate ExoSAP enzyme components
 - store at 4°C or -20°C (long term storage)
17. Prepare sequencing reaction
- Note:
- sequence products from both directions with primers used for the nested PCR (2nd PCR)
 - This protocol is validated from our in-house sequencing facility, but may be different in other laboratories

	Reaction	x ____ (samples)
Primer (10mM)	0,5 µl	_____ µl
BigDye 3.1	0,5 µl	_____ µl
5x Buffer	1,5 µl	_____ µl
H₂O (HPLC grade)	6,0 µl	_____ µl
PCR-product (10-20 ng/µl)	1,5 µl	
final volume	10,0 µl	

18. Run sequencing reaction in PCR cycler using following conditions:
- 1) 96°C 1-2 min
 - 2) 96°C 10sec
 - 3) 58°C 5sec
 - 4) 60°C 4min
 - 5) 4°C hold
- 25 cycles

Annex 1

Table 1: List of primer sequences. Primers for nested PCR (2nd PCR) are highlighted in grey.

Marker	Oligoname	Sequence	Amplicon size
2	2_448 F	AAGGGCTTGACGGAGAAGAG	621
2	2_1068 R	CCGAACACAAATCTTCCGCG	
2	2_451 F	GGCTTGACGGAGAAGAGGAT	593
2	2_1043 R	TACGCACTCAGAAAGGCTGG	
7	7_362 F	CCTTGCTATCCGGGATGTCC	724
7	7_1085 R	CATGCCAGACTCTGTTCCGT	
7	7_481 F	GTGGCATGAGTATAGGGGGC	577
7	7_1082 R	GCCAGACTCTGTTCCGTAGC	
8	8_125 F	GCAATTCAAGAAAGTGGCCCA	700
8	8_824 R	GCGTTGGGGTGGGAAAGATA	
8	8_149 F	GGAAGGGACTATGTGAGAGCT	570
8	8_718 R	CTGTGAGGCACTGGAAGAGG	
10	10_1510 F	CGGCAAACAGTGTTCCCTTGG	799
10	10_2308 R	CAGCGACTTGGAAAGCCTTCT	
10	10_1521 F	GTTCCCTTGGAGACCAGGAGC	598
10	10_2118 R	AAAACCGTCAGCTGCAATGC	
11	11_1625 F	ATGCCTATGGTCGTGTCAGC	795
11	11_2419 R	GCCTGTCACCCCAGTTTTA	
11	11_1650 F	GGTACGACAAGCACACCTCA	629
11	11_2271 R	GATGCGCTCCTCAGTAAGCT	
14	14_1569 F	GGCAGACGCGTTAACCTTTG	809
14	14_2377 R	CCAGAAATATACAGGGCCAGACA	
14	14_1806 F	AGGGCTGTGTTGAGTGTTGT	536
14	14_2341 R	CGGCCATTGCAGACGATG	
20	20_480 F	GCCCATGCTGATCTCATCCA	987
20	20_1463 R	TGACTCGTGCTCTGAAACCG	
20	20_630 F	GCAAAGAGCACTACCGTTGT	656
20	20_1285 R	TCCCGTCCAGAACCACAAAA	